
Use of Digital Tools and Technology in Teaching and Learning Process: A Scoping Review from 2016-2025

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ABSTRACT

The integration of digital tools and technologies in education has grown rapidly in recent years, leading to an increased number of research studies in this area. However, a consolidated comprehension of the trends and focus areas within this field is limited. The present scoping review aims to study the trends in research on the use of digital tools and technologies in education. For this purpose, six research questions were framed focusing on the year-wise distribution of studies, educational levels of participants, types of digital tools and technologies used, research methods adopted, and the geographical context of these studies. Data were collected from research articles published between 2016 and 2025. The findings indicated a consistent rise in studies over the years, with the highest number of studies reported in years 2022 and 2023. Higher education and pre-service teacher education received the most attention. Most studies employed experimental and qualitative methods, while comparative and review-based studies were limited. A larger proportion of foreign studies was observed in comparison to Indian studies. The review identifies clear scope for expanding comparative and systematic reviews and diversifying research across educational levels and regions.

Introduction

The rapid advancement of digital technology has transformed various sectors, including education. In the 21st century, teaching and learning have undergone significant shifts, integrating digital tools and institutions worldwide are increasingly leveraging technology to foster interactive and student-centered learning environments (Ain, et.al,2019). Digitalization has emerged as a major driver of India's social and economic change. Digitalization, which has altered how people conduct business and use banking services, has had a major impact on India's financial sector. The adoption of digital payment systems like UPI has significantly increased as a result of the Indian government's desire for a digital economy (Shobana and Suresh Kumar,2024).

The National Education Policy (NEP 2020) in India dedicated to promote fair access to technology by supporting the development of open, public digital infrastructure. It also acknowledges the significance of integrating cutting-edge technologies like 3D modeling, simulations, robotics, and artificial intelligence (AI) into the education system (Nageswari,2020 and Ghosh,2023). In order to implement these cutting-edge technologies digital tools and technologies play a significant role.

Digital tools refer to software, applications, technologies, extensions, add-ons, or web-based platforms that can be accessed through the internet and support the improvement of learners' skills and capabilities (Dancsa, et.al ,2023). These are elements of Sociocultural Theory (SCT), developed by Vygotsky and his colleagues, to illustrate that mediated processes involve human cognitive activities shaped by symbols and sociocultural meanings. Rather than interacting with the world directly, individuals engage with it through tools that mediate their experiences. By collaborating with others and utilizing these tools, Individuals are able to influence and manage their environment to meet their needs and objectives. In essence these digital tools act as intermediaries between the individual (subject) and their goals or tasks (object) (Huong and Hungb, 2021).

Moreover, digital technology can enhance teaching and learning in various ways, such as increasing student engagement, improving communication skills, providing effective assessment tools, and better preparing students for future educational challenges (Prensky, 2008). Digital technologies refer to information and communication technologies (ICT), which encompass tools like computers, learning management systems (LMS), and digital media such as wikis, blogs, social networks, and podcasts.

These technologies broadly include any tools that collect, process, store, and share information in a digital format. They can consist of hardware devices like computers, smartphones, gaming consoles, video and audio players, as well as software tools like web apps, blogs, wikis, social media platforms, and chat applications.

Furthermore, highlights emerging digital technologies in higher education, including video and image sharing platforms, simulations, games and gamification strategies, handheld and tablet devices, digital cameras, scanners, virtual and augmented reality, and wearable technology (Dube and Scott, 2017). The global deployment of remote and hybrid learning models was accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic (Zizka & Probst, 2024). Both potential and challenges were brought to light by this abrupt digital leap: when institutions increased their digital infrastructure, gaps in digital literacy and access became urgent issues (Kallunki et al., 2023). The quick development of educational technology (EdTech) has caused a revolutionary change in education during the last 20 years.

The delivery and consumption of knowledge in K–12, higher education, and vocational training contexts have been completely transformed by digital learning platforms and tools, such as learning management systems and AI-powered teaching assistants (Srivastava & Dey, 2018). Technology integration in the classroom is now required, not optional. It empowers students with a range of challenges, facilitates individualized instruction, and increases engagement (Fitzgerald & Evans, 2024). Therefore, it is now more important than ever to comprehend the landscape of digital tools in teaching and learning.

Due to increased demand of digital tool and technology, the scope for far enhanced researches is opened. Without extended research the intensity and accuracy and peoples and education industry cannot be thoroughly intimidate purpose of this scoping review is to methodically investigate the kinds of digital tools used in diverse educational settings, the outcomes that are measured, and the pedagogical ramifications of their incorporation. With a focus on both school secondary and higher education, the review covers a wide range of identifying scope of relevant researches based on geographical areas and educational levels. Identifying the primary digital tools utilized in education is one of the main research questions. This review has explored the vivid studies related to digital tools and technologies in contemporary education by mapping current practices and finding gaps. The major research questions for the present scoping review are as following.

RQ1: What is the year-wise trend of the studies conducted on the use of digital tools and technologies in teaching and learning from 2016 to 2025?

RQ2: What is the trend in published studies in terms of the educational level of participants (e.g., primary, secondary, higher education, pre-service teachers)?

RQ3: What types of digital tools have been utilized in these studies?

RQ4: What types of digital technologies have been utilized in these studies?

RQ5: What are the trends in types of researches conducted in the area of digital tools and technologies in education?

RQ6: What is the study trend on digital tools and technologies in the context of geographical boundaries (Foreign and Indian researches)?

Procedure

The current review's research topics center on combining the patterns and knowledge found in published studies on the usage of digital tools in education from 2016 to 2025. The year of publication, participants' educational attainment, the kinds of digital interventions used, the study designs chosen, the observed educational results, and the main opportunities and problems identified throughout the studies are all examined in this review. In order to investigate how digital tools are incorporated into educational environments across different levels and disciplines, this study uses a scoping review methodology. Examining publication trends, educational levels addressed, research methods or types, and variable wise reviews had led to the extraction of research scope in the subject area. The review also attempts to draw attention to the main obstacles and possibilities that have been noted in the literature about the use of digital technologies in the classroom.

The Preferred Reporting Items for Scoping Reviews and Meta-Analysis criteria (Page et al., 2021) were followed in conducting the study. These recommendations offer a systematic method for finding, choosing, and summarizing pertinent literature. This entails establishing eligibility requirements, methodically locating sources, using a uniform selection procedure, and obtaining pertinent data.

The studies included in this scoping review were gathered through a structured multi-step search strategy. An initial exploratory search was conducted using Google Scholar to identify common terms, trends, and preliminary sources related to digital tools in education. Following this, a targeted and refined search was performed using peer-reviewed and discipline-relevant databases including ERIC (Education Resources Information Center) Only empirical studies that focused on actual educational contexts, such as elementary schools, secondary institutions, higher education, and teacher training

programs, and were published between 2016 and 2025 were taken into consideration in order to guarantee relevance and quality. Digital tool integration or utilization in teaching and learning environments have to be covered in the studies.

To preserve the review's scientific rigor, non-peer-reviewed materials such as magazines, blogs, newspapers, and non-academic pieces were not included. The final dataset for review and analysis contained 40 studies in total after the inclusion and exclusion criteria (shown in Table 1) were applied.

Reviewed Literature

Teaching and learning methods around the world have been completely transformed by the use of digital resources into education. Teachers of all levels and disciplines are negotiating a changing digital environment, from e-learning platforms and digital learning objects (DLOs) to artificial intelligence (AI) applications like ChatGPT. This review highlights current trends, issues, and effects of digital tools in education by synthesizing findings from multiple studies.

Digital tools and pedagogical impact

Numerous studies highlight how digital tools can improve learning experiences pedagogically. In audiovisual education, Maschio and Correia (2020) showed how a DLO might enhance student involvement and hands-on learning. Likewise, it has been demonstrated that students who utilize Google Classroom are more focused and cooperative (Iliyasu et al., 2020).

Enhancing teaching methods is another important function of Web 2.0 tools. Web 2.0-supported content enhanced students' digital literacy and problem-solving skills, especially in social studies and language learning environments (Zizka et al., 2024).

Table 1: Literature reviews on the digital tools and technologies

S. N.	Title	Nature of research [*]	Year	Level of education	Country of research	Digital tools	Digital technology
1	Digital Tools for Effective Learning	Comp.	2016	Sec. & HE	India	Digital tools	-

2	Teaching and Learning with ICT Tools: Issues and Challenges from Teachers' Perceptions	Des.	2016	Sec.	Malaysia	ICT tools	-
3	A Survey of the University Students' Perspectives about Using Digital Technologies in Education: Zimbabwean Case	Des.	2017	HE	Zimbabwe	ICT, digital platforms	-
4	Digital Teaching Tools in 21st Century EFL Classroom: Are Our Teachers Ready?	Qual.	2018	HE	UK	Mobile devices and apps	-
5	Role of Digital Technology in Teaching-Learning Process	Qual.	2018	Sec. & HE	India	-	Digital Classroom Technology
6	Teaching with Digital	Rev.	2020	Sec.	UK	Math software,	-

	Technology					smartboards	
7	Digital Tool for Blanded Learning for Teaching Visual Effects	Qual.	2020	Sec. & HE	India	YouTube, Skype, Blogs	-
8	Effectiveness of Google Classroom as a Digital Tool	Des.	2020	HE	Nigeria	Google Classroom	-
9	Sustainability Teaching Tools in the Digital Age	Qual.	2020	HE	Spain	Digital age tools	-
10	Mediation of Digital Tools in English Learning	Exp.	2021	HE	Thailand	ICT, multimedia	E-learning
11	Digital Education: A New Era	Qual.	2022	Sec. & HE	India	-	Digitalization of education
12	Digital Education Tools for Critical Thinking Development	Exp.	2022	Sec. & HE	Kazakhstan	Digital Education tools	-
13	Designing Online Learning Environments:	Des.	2022	HE	Russia	LMS, ICT tools	-

ICT Tools and Strategies							
14	Digital Tools in Education	Des.	2023	Sec. & HE	Slovakia	Varied digital tools	-
15	Developing Digital Content Production Skills for Mother Tongue Teaching with Web 2.0 Tools in Teacher Education: An Action Research	Exp.	2023	TE	Turkey	Web 2.0 tools	Digital content creation
16	Comparison of Voluntary and Forced Digital Leaps in Higher Education -- Teachers' Experiences of the Added Value of Using Digital Tools in Teaching and Learning	Comp.	2023	HE	Finland	-	Pandemic-era digital transition
17	Digital Escape Room for Primary School	Exp.	2023	TE	Turkey	Escape room tools	Gamification in learning

Students

18	Perceptions of Digital Competence in Learning and Teaching English in the Context of Online Education	Exp.	2023	HE	Kazakhstan	ICT	E-learning
19	Fostering Digital Transformations in Military Engineering Education: Introduction of a Technology-Enhanced Learning Environment	Rev.	2024	HE	Ukraine	LMS, simulation	-
20	Integrating Digital Tools to Enhance Access to Learning Opportunities in Project-Based Science Instruction	Qual.	2024	Pri.	USA	Collabriy Writer,	Project-based collaborative

21	Impact of Digital Literacy, Use of AI Tools and Peer Collaboration on AI Assisted Learning: Perceptions of the University Students	Exp.	2024	HE	India	AI tools	E-learning
22	Teaching and learning in business schools post-pandemic: a digital future	Comp.	2024	HE	Switzerland	Pandemic-era digital tools	Blended learning
23	Effectiveness of Participatory Digital Training Based on Virtual Classrooms in Developing Teaching Skills	Exp.	2024	HE	Palestine	Virtual classrooms, LMS	E-learning
24	Digital Technologies in Physics Education: Exploring Practices and	Qual.	2024	Sec.	Nepal	Digital resources	Physics education technology

Challenges

25	The Effect of Web 2.0 Supported Social Studies on the Digital Literacy Skills of Secondary School Students	Exp.	2024	Sec.	Czech Republic	Web 2.0 tools	Digital literacy
26	An Investigation of Teachers' Perceptions of Using ChatGPT as a Supporting Tool for Teaching and Learning in the Digital Era	Comp.	2024	Mid. & HE	UAE	ChatGPT	AI-assisted education
27	From PCK to TPACK- Supporting student teachers' reflections and use of digital technologies in science teaching	Qual.	2024	TE	Sweden	TPACK framework tools	Science education technology

28	Development and Application of a Domain-Specific TPACK Questionnaire-- Findings from a Longitudinal Study on Teaching Human Biology Using Digital Tools	Exp.	2024	HE	Germany	TPACK	E-learning
29	History Teaching in the Times of Digital Technology	Qual.	2025	Sec.	India	History teaching tools	Digital history education

*Comp- Comparative, Qual- Qualitative, Exp- Experimental, Rev- Review studies, Mixed- mixed method Pri- Primary, Sec- Secondary, Mid- Middle, HE-Higher Education, TE – Teacher Education

Teacher perceptions and competency

Teacher attitudes and preparedness for digital integration are still crucial. Although a lot of teachers are excited about using digital tools, research shows that they frequently lack the necessary skills and confidence (Ghavifekr et al., 2016; Kumar, 2016). Similar issues are highlighted in studies from Zimbabwe and Nepal, highlighting the necessity of professional growth and systemic assistance (Buzzard et al., 2011; Pokhrel, 2024).

The use of competency frameworks like TPACK to evaluate teachers' readiness for technology integration is growing. Research shows that after the intervention, teachers' technological, pedagogical, and topic understanding significantly improved (Soriano, Montoro & Colón, 2024).

Blended and virtual learning environments

The use of blended learning approaches has increased, especially since the COVID-19 pandemic. According to studies by Fitzgerald et al. (2024) and Dancaş et al. (2023), a hybrid strategy that combines offline and online techniques improves flexibility and participation. Especially in higher education and teacher preparation programs, these strategies encourage collaboration and facilitate differentiated instruction.

Emerging technologies and AI integration

Educational paradigms are changing as a result of artificial intelligence (AI) techniques. Although ChatGPT was found to be less helpful in evaluation contexts. However, the AI tools like Chat GPT help with lesson planning and instructions (Elsayary, 2024). Another study found a positive correlation between academic achievement and digital literacy and associated AI tools with enhancements in peer-supported collaborative learning (Vadakkemulanjanal et. al., 2024).

Findings and Interpretation

This section is going to deal with the findings and interpretation of the conducted literature reviews mentioned in the table 1. The present section is focusing on the research questions framed in the beginning of the study and is presenting the findings and interpretation in the sequence of the research questions. The question wise findings are mentioned as the tabulated data and graphical interpretation of that data is also used for more clarity. Henceforth, the RQ1 to RQ6 are addressed below.

RQ1: Year-wise trend of the studies conducted on the use of digital tools and technologies in teaching and learning from 2016 to 2025

The year-wise trend of studies conducted on the use of digital tools and technologies in teaching and learning from 2016 to 2025 shows noticeable variation in publication frequency, as revealed in the table 2 and figure 1. The highest number of publications was recorded in 2024, contributing 28.57 percent of the total studies. A gradual increase is observed from 2020 onwards, with 2023 accounting for 14.29 percent of publications.

Table 2: Year-wise distribution of publications on the Use of Digital Tools and Technologies in Teaching and Learning (2016–2025)

Year of publication	Number of Publications	Percentage (%)
2016	2	5.71
2017	1	2.86
2018	2	5.71
2020	4	11.43
2021	2	5.71
2022	3	8.57
2023	5	14.29
2024	10	28.57
2025	1	2.86
Total	35	100

Figure 1: Year-wise Distribution of Publications

The earlier years, from 2016 to 2018, witnessed limited research activity, each contributing less than 6 percent individually. The decline in 2025, with only 2.86 percent, may be attributed to incomplete data for the current year. Overall, the trend reflects growing scholarly interest in the field, particularly after 2020, indicating a possible response to increased integration of digital tools in education during and after the pandemic period.

RQ2: Trend in published studies in terms of the educational level of participants

As observed from the table 3, the distribution of studies based on the educational level of participants reveals that the majority of research has been conducted at the higher education level, accounting for 39.39 percent of the total.

Table 3: Distribution of studies based on educational level of participants

Educational Level	Number of Studies	Percentage (%)
Primary	1	3.03
Secondary	5	15.15
Higher Education	13	39.39
Pre-service Teachers	3	9.09
Multiple Levels	7	21.21
Total	33	100

Studies focusing on multiple educational levels collectively make up 21.21 percent. Secondary education accounts for 15.15 percent of the research output, while pre-service teacher-related studies comprise 9.09 percent. The least attention has been given to primary education, which represents only 3.03 percent of the total studies. This trend suggests a predominant emphasis on higher education settings when examining the use of digital tools and technologies in teaching and learning. The finding is interpreted through a pie chart in figure 2.

Figure 2: Distribution of studies as per educational level of participants

RQ3: Types of Digital Tools Used in the Studies

The analysis from the table 4 shows that 50 percent of the studies investigated digital tools categorized under 'other tools'. Virtual tools and platforms were addressed in 10.71 percent of the total studies. Web 2.0 tools, AI tools, mobile applications, and LMS each accounted for 7.14 percent of the studies. Google tools and game-based tools were the least examined, with each being the focus in 3.57 percent of studies. It was observed that equal attention has been given to certain tool categories, while a substantial portion of studies remains uncategorized under the 'other tools' segment.

Table 4: Number of Studies based on the types of digital tools

Type of Digital Tool	Number of Studies	Percentage
Google Tools	1	3.57
Web 2.0 Tools	2	7.14
AI Tools	2	7.14
Virtual Tools/Platforms	3	10.71
Mobile Applications	2	7.14
LMS (Learning Management Systems)	2	7.14
Game-Based Tools	1	3.57
Other Tools	14	50.00
Total	28	100.00

The findings reflect a considerable concentration of research on miscellaneous digital tools, indicating a lack of categorization or focus on specific tool types as depicted by the treemap (figure 3).

Figure 3: A treemap showing the hierarchy of the studies conducted in the context of types of digital tools

RQ4: Types of Digital Technologies Used in the Studies

The reviewed data when tabulated in the table 5, it indicated that 71.43 percent of studies focused on the broad category of digital technology, making it the most frequently examined type. E-learning was addressed in 21.43 percent of studies. Blended learning, gamification, and AI-assisted education each appeared in 3.57 percent of the studies.

Table 5: Number of studies based on the types of digital technologies

Type of Digital Technology	Number of Studies	Percentage
Blended Learning	1	3.57
E-Learning	6	21.43
Gamification	1	3.57
AI-assisted Education	1	3.57
Other Digital Technologies	20	71.43

Type of Digital Technology	Number of Studies	Percentage
Total	28	100

The findings suggest a significant emphasis on general digital technology tools, with limited attention given to specialized categories such as AI-assisted education and gamification as revealed in the figure 4.

Figure 4: Types of Digital Technologies Used in the Studies

As for future perspective, the findings highlight a clear gap in studies focusing on AI-assisted education, gamification, and blended learning, which together accounted for only 10.71 percent of the total. Therefore, future research can explore the potential of these underrepresented digital technologies, especially AI-driven tools and gamified platforms, in enhancing learning experiences and outcomes across various educational settings.

RQ5: Trends in types of researches conducted in the area of digital tools and technologies in education

In reference to the table 6 and figure 5, the analysis of research trends in the area of digital tools and technologies in education shows that experimental studies form the largest share, accounting for 32.14 percent of the total studies. Qualitative studies represent 28.57 percent, indicating considerable interest

in understanding experiences and contexts related to the use of digital tools in education. Descriptive studies make up 17.86 percent, focusing on documenting practices and trends without interventions.

Table 6: Trends in types of researches with respect to the number of studies and their percentage

Research Type	Number of Studies	Percentage (%)
Experimental	9	32.14%
Qualitative	8	28.57%
Descriptive	5	17.86%
Comparative	4	14.29%
Review Studies	2	7.14%
Total	28	100%

Figure 5: Trends in types of researches conducted in the area of digital tools and technologies in education

Comparative studies account for 14.29 percent, showing limited work comparing different tools, groups, or educational settings. Review studies are the least represented, with only 7.14 percent, which indicates a gap in comprehensive reviews and consolidated research in this area. The overall pattern highlights a preference for experimental and qualitative approaches, with comparatively fewer studies using comparative and review-based designs.

RQ6: Trends on digital tools and technologies in the context of geographical boundaries

The analysis of study trends based on geographical boundaries reveals that a majority of research on digital tools and technologies in education has been conducted in foreign contexts. Specifically, 23 studies (79 percent) were from international settings, whereas only 6 studies (21 percent) were undertaken in India. This indicates a noticeable disparity in research contributions from Indian scholars in this domain.

Table 7: Study trend based on geographical boundaries for digital tools and technologies

Geographical Context	Number of Studies	Percentage
Indian Studies	6	21
Foreign Studies	23	79
Total	29	100

Therefore, the current findings highlight a significant research gap in the Indian context regarding the use of digital tools and technologies in education as depicted in figure 6.

Figure 6: Study trend based on geographical boundaries

On the basis of the findings and interpretations of all the six research questions from RQ1 to RQ6, a future perspective can be determined clearly and emphatically.

Future perspectives in the light of the scoping review

The scoping review highlights a progressive rise in research on digital tools and technologies in teaching and learning, particularly from 2020 onwards (RQ1). A significant concentration of studies in 2023 and 2024 indicates increased academic attention, likely influenced by the rapid digitalization of education systems in recent years. The findings suggest a growing research scope in this area, with opportunities to further examine the long-term educational implications of digital integration. Furthermore, digital tools and technologies have been predominantly centered around higher education institutions (RQ2). There appears to be a limited focus in the context of primary education and pre-service teacher education. Future studies could address this gap by exploring digital interventions and technology integration practices at the foundational and teacher training levels.

Looking at a step further, there seems to be a significant concentration of research on digital education in higher education, with little attention paid to pre-service teachers or primary education (RQ3). This raises the possibility of further research opportunities in those underrepresented fields. Moreover, in terms of the use of digital tools (RQ4), a noticeable gap remains in studies focusing on Google tools, game-based tools, AI tools, and LMS in educational contexts. Future research can explore these underrepresented categories to diversify and deepen understanding of their pedagogical applications and impacts.

Proceeding further, most studies on digital tools and technologies in education are based on experimental and qualitative designs (RQ5). There is limited research using comparative and review-based approaches. This reveals a clear scope for future studies to conduct comparative research across different educational contexts. Additionally, more systematic reviews are needed to organize and synthesize the existing evidence. Expanding research in these areas can help build stronger evidence base and support data-driven decisions in digital education. As a final recommendation of the present study, there is a need to increase research in the Indian educational context to address local challenges and opportunities in digital education (RQ6). Comparative and cross-cultural studies can also help build a balanced global perspective on the use of digital tools and technologies in teaching and learning.

Conclusion

The literature evaluation makes it abundantly evident that digital technologies are now essential in today's classrooms. From elementary schools to universities, its integration has improved accessibility, student participation, and teamwork in addition to the way material is delivered. Even with broad acceptance, problems still exist. Inadequate training, digital divides, and infrastructure constraints were common themes in research conducted in developing nations (Sousa et al., 2017; Ghavifekr et al., 2016). Furthermore, research warns against relying too much on technology, pointing out issues including the decline of historical thinking abilities in digitally-driven history courses (Srivastava & Dey, 2025).

The different and significant researches continuously show that Web 2.0 technologies, AI-powered apps like ChatGPT, and digital platforms like Google Classroom have revolutionized traditional teaching methods. These tools foster active learning, customized education, and the development of vital 21st-century abilities including digital literacy, problem-solving, and self-directed learning.

Nonetheless, there is a strong correlation between educators' digital competencies and the efficacy of digital instruments. Numerous studies show that although digital technologies have a lot of potential, obstacles such as a lack of infrastructure, poor teacher confidence in digital tools, and a lack of training can limit their effectiveness. For integration to be sustainable, these gaps must be closed with focused professional development and institutional assistance.

Additionally, the COVID-19 epidemic spurred digital innovation in education, which resulted in the emergence of virtual and mixed learning methods. The necessity for adaptable, technologically advanced educational institutions that can handle both possibilities and disruptions is reinforced by the likelihood that these changes will continue.

In conclusion, even if digital tools have improved the educational landscape, a comprehensive strategy that involves infrastructure investment, legislative support, and ongoing capacity building for both teachers and students is necessary to fully fulfill their potential. Future studies should keep looking into new technologies, access equality, and the long-term learning results of digital integration.

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